

FLEXIBLE CAPACITIVE COMPOSITE NEURAL ELECTRODES AND SIMPLIFIED FABRICATION ENABLED BY THERMAL RELEASE TAPE

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ABSTRACT

Stretchable/flexible neural electrode arrays play critical roles in understanding cognitive functions of brain and targeted treatments for neurological and psychiatric disorders. Here, a flexible capacitive neural electrode design using polyimide-Barium Titanate (PI-BTO) composite film is presented. With the high dielectric constant (31, 7~8 times higher than pure PI), dense neural electrode array design is accomplished by using the PI-BTO composite film as the top layer. Its ability to obtain accurate multichannel ECoG signals from brain is verified by *in-vivo* experiments. Meanwhile, in order to optimize transfer printing process in flexible neural electrodes fabrication, we also present a thermal release tape (TRT) transfer printing approach to fabricate stretchable neural electrodes. Due to the large strong to weak adhesion ratio of TRT, the fabrication process is simplified by avoiding the sacrifice layer preparation in transfer printing process. The as-fabricated electrode arrays by thermal release tape transfer printing are proved by the collection of high quality ECoG signals of rat.

1 INTRODUCTION

Neural electrodes play important roles in diagnosing and treating neurological disorders such as epilepsy, Parkinson's disease and chronic pain^[1]. Emphasis in neural electrode is placed on efforts to improve the biocompatibility and functionality by considering their biomechanics, novel materials, and fabrication methods^[2]. Previous studies illustrate the flexible neural electrode, with their thinness and softness, lead to forming conformal physical contact on the nonplanar surface of brain for better signal recording^[2]. Therefore, the flexible neural electrodes placed in the neural plane have been widely used to monitor and modulate the neural signals, including recording electrocorticography (ECoG) signals from the cortical surface^[3], cortical stimulation in the motor cortex^[3] and chemical sensing of dopamine^[4]. As for acquisition of the biomedical signal, the capacitive electrodes have the unique advantage: enhanced safety. Since the conductive layer of capacitive electrode is fully encapsulated by dielectric materials^[5], the brain will not contact with the conductive layer directly and the potential danger of current leakage and electrical short can be avoid. Thus, the flexible capacitive electrode, featuring the flexibility and safety together, is a promising candidate for the novel neural electrode array design for biomedical applications. Capacitive coupling through the dielectric layer provides the basis for detecting ECoG signals by capacitive electrode array. For the capacitive electrode array, the key parameters of capacitance (C) are ϵ_0 , ϵ_r , d and S , which can be determined by

$$C = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r S}{d} \quad (1)$$

Where ϵ_r is the relative dielectric constant of the dielectric layer, ϵ_0 is the vacuum dielectric constant, S is the coupling area of the electrode, d is the distance between the dura mater and the electrode. According to Equation (1), due to the limitations of space and adhesion performance, the improvement of C can only rely on the increase of ϵ_r . However, the dielectric performance of current flexible materials still cannot meet the need for the capacitive electrode. Consequently, looking for an advanced dielectric layer material with high dielectric constant is the crux to develop a feasible capacitive ECoG electrode.

Here, a flexible capacitive electrode with polyimide-Barium Titanate (PI-BTO) composite film is presented. Polyimide (PI) is a flexible polymer with excellent insulativity and mechanical properties,

which is often used as a flexible passivation layer to reinforce the metal layers^[2]. Meanwhile, Barium titanate (BTO) is a ferroelectric material with high dielectric constant and low losses above room temperature, which is widely applied in a many fields, such as high-capacity memory cells^[6], multilayer ceramic capacitors (MLCCs)^[7,8], ultrasonic machines^[9], nonlinear resistors^[10] and positive temperature coefficient of resistance thermistors (PTCRs)^[11]. Combining the flexibility of PI and dielectric performance of BTO by doping BTO in the PI, a flexible dielectric material can be obtained. By using this flexible dielectric as the encapsulation layer for the capacitive neural electrode, a capacitive electrode array is accomplished for acquiring accurate ECoG signals from brain of anesthetized rat. 3D finite element analysis (FEA) demonstrates that the flexible capacitive electrode with PI-BTO composite material can maintain good mechanical reliability when it is twisted by about 45° . Moreover, in order to avoid complex transfer printing process in flexible neural electrodes fabrication^[12-17], we also present a thermal release tape (TRT) transfer printing approach to fabricate flexible neural devices, which does not require sacrifice layer preparation in transfer printing process. Using this method, a flexible neural electrode is fabricated by transferring and printing the functional membrane to ultrathin PDMS substrate. The as-fabricated electrode shows excellent mechanical and electrical properties, which are evaluated by FEA and *in-vivo* experiments. When the as-fabricated electrode cover the dura mater of rat, the accurately ECoG signals could be acquired due to good conformal contact between electrodes and the brain. The principles of TRT process are also discussed with related mechanical model.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: a) Schematic illustration of flexible capacitive electrodes. b) The relation between frequency and dielectric constant of PI-BTO composite and pure PI. c) The strain (ϵ_{\max}) distribution of Au layer derived from FEA results when the electrode is twisted at an angle of 45° . d) Representative ECoG

signals recorded by capacitive PI-BTO composite electrode array (up) and stainless-steel screw electrodes (down).

Fig. 1a shows the layered structure of the capacitive electrode array with a PI-BTO layer. The layout of the Au conductive layer includes three parts: the output part, the interconnect part and the input part. The input part is designed as four square pads to collect ECoG signals. When the capacitive electrode array contacts to the dura mater of anesthetized rats, a capacitor structure formed with the rat's dura mater, the PI-BTO composite and Au layer of capacitive electrode. PI-BTO composites between the Au layer and dura mater of rat act as dielectric layer of the capacitor.

In this work, PI-BTO composite is selected as the dielectric layer of the capacitive electrode. The PI-BTO composite was prepared by in-situ polymerization. 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTS) was used as a coupling agent for BaTiO₃ and polyimide in order to improve the uniformity of the composite. With the purpose of ensuring excellent dispersion and dielectric properties, we choose the PI-BTO composite material with BaTiO₃ content of 40 wt% as the dielectric layer of the capacitive electrode. The dielectric properties of the PI-BTO composite and pure PI are measured by the impedance analyser (Agilent 4294A). As shown in Fig. 1b, at the frequency ranging from 1 kHz to 100 kHz, the dielectric constant of PI-BTO composite is about 31, which is as 7 to 8 times as that of pure PI (about 4.0). The growth of dielectric constant can provide the increasing of capacitive coupling for capacitive electrode array, which is beneficial to obtain high-quality representative ECoG signals.

Figure 2: a) The relationship between velocity and energy release rate of PI/Glass interface (orange line), PDMS/PI interface (dark yellow line) at 20°C, and TRT/PI interface at 20°C (black line), 70°C (red line), 80°C (green line) and 100°C (light magen line). b) Schematic illustration of resistive-type electrodes. c) The FEA strain distribution results of resistive-type electrodes when twisting at an angle of 90°. d) Representative ECoG signals recorded by stretchable neural electrode array (top) and stainless-steel screw electrodes (down).

The mechanical properties of the capacitive PI-BTO composite electrode arrays have been analysed with finite element analysis (FEA). The FEA results of twisting at an angle of 45° indicate that the average principal strain in the metals is less than the fracture strain of Au ($\approx 1\%$)^[2], demonstrating an ability to offer superior mechanical attributes for capacitive electrode to accommodate natural motions.

The application of capacitive PI-BTO composite electrode arrays is also verified by *in-vivo* experiments. Fig. 1d illustrates the high-quality ECoG signals simultaneously recorded by the flexible capacitive PI-BTO composite electrode array (up) and the screw electrodes (down). The signal amplitude of capacitive PI-BTO electrode array is similar with that of conventional screw electrodes, which reveal the feasibility of capacitive PI-BTO electrode array to detecting ECoG signals.

With the intention of avoiding complex transfer printing process in flexible neural electrodes fabrication, we also present a simple transfer printing method to fabricate metal/polyimide based flexible neural electrodes. This method is accomplished by using thermal release tape and does not require sacrifice layer preparation in transfer printing process. Since the adhesion of TRT depends on temperature, the energy release rate of TRT/PI interface is also temperature-related. As shown in Fig. 2a, the energy release rate of TRT/PI interface shows a sharp drop when it is heated to around 100°C . Besides, the effect of peeling velocity on the energy release rate has also been carefully studied. It is observed that a larger critical energy release rate of TRT/PI and PDMS/PI interfaces can be obtained by increasing the peeling velocity. The energy release rate of PI/Glass is larger than that of PDMS/PI interface and smaller than that of TRT/PI interface. Due to TRT's large adhesion at temperature of 20°C and small adhesion at 100°C , the metal/polyimide based electrodes with stretchable serpentine design can be picked up directly from glass substrate, and printed to PDMS (polydimethylsiloxane) substrate.

Using the thermal release tape transfer printing method, the stretchable neural electrodes arrays are fabricated. As shown in Fig. 2b, the stretchable neural electrodes arrays are composed of nine-channels with a three-layered serpentine-like interconnect structure. The Au layer encapsulated with polyimide serve as the conductive layer to detect the ECoG signal. Similarly with above capacitive electrode, the layout of the Au conductive layer also includes three parts: the output part, the interconnect part and the input part. The output part is designed as parallel square pads to connect with the heat seal connector (HSC) and cable of ECoG recorder. Nine circles, serving as the input part, are linked with the output part through the serpentine interconnectors.

The mechanical properties of resistive-type electrodes with stretchable designs have also been analysed, which is shown in Fig. 2c. The resistive-type electrodes with stretchable designs can be twisted by $\approx 90^\circ$. When twisting at an angle of 90° , the maximum principal strain of half the width of any section in the Au layer is smaller than 0.3% (no elastic-plastic transition happened)^[2], illustrating the resistive-type electrodes with stretchable designs exhibited good mechanical reliability.

Fig. 2d demonstrates ECoG signals recorded by stretchable neural electrode array and stainless-steel screw electrodes. The ECoG signals recorded by as-fabricated electrode array have been compared with stainless-steel screw electrodes. High quality ECoG signals of anesthetized rat is collected with the as-fabricated electrode array, indicating an excellent conformal contact between the electrode array and the curved surface of dura mater.

3 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we present a capacitive PI-BTO composite ECoG electrode array with the high dielectric constant (31, 7~8 times higher than pure PI). The capacitive PI-BTO composite electrode array has been successfully used to detect representative ECoG signals. Meanwhile, a simple thermal release tape transfer printing method is developed to fabricate the resistive-type electrode arrays with stretchable designs. Both the capacitive electrode arrays and resistive-type electrode arrays have good mechanical attributes, which are proved by FEA results. The resistive-type electrode array can be conformably attached to the dura mater, which has been used to obtain high quality ECoG signals of anesthetized rat.

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